

Realistic Capacity Scaling of Single-Band and Multi-Band Optical Transport Systems

André Souza
Nokia, Optical Networks
Carnaxide, Portugal
andre.souza@nokia.com

Antonio Napoli
Nokia, Optical Networks
Munich, Germany
antonio.napoli@nokia.com

João Pedro
Nokia, Optical Networks
Instituto de Telecomunicações, IST
joao.pedro@nokia.com

Abstract—The exponential growth in global data traffic is driving the need for higher-capacity optical communication systems. One promising solution is the expansion of the transmission bandwidth through multi-band (MB) systems, leveraging the full low-loss spectral window of standard single-mode fiber (ITU-T G.652D), which spans approximately 54 THz. While this approach offers a theoretical tenfold increase in bandwidth over conventional C-band only systems, practical limitations, such as (i) increased attenuation, (ii) reduced amplifier performance outside the C-band, and (iii) the impact of wideband effects such as stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) constrain the achievable capacity gains. This article explores strategies to overcome these limitations, including the extension of amplifier bandwidth within the C-band to 6 THz and the integration of MB transmission with spatial-division multiplexing (SDM) techniques. We conduct a comparative analysis of single-band and multi-band transmission systems, exploring configurations from a single 6-THz super band up to a full four-super-band system spanning 24 THz. To reduce the impact of SRS and associated system complexity, we cap the maximum contiguous spectral occupation at 18 THz (equivalent to three super bands). As a result, the system employing more than three super bands includes a guard band of more than 14 THz. The study highlights the trade-offs between spectral efficiency, system complexity, and capacity and cost, providing insights into the design of next-generation optical networks that balance capacity and complexity.

Index Terms—Multi-band transmission, Capacity scaling, Optical communications, Optical transport networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

C-band-only systems are rapidly approaching their fundamental limit. Recent key drivers of traffic growth in optical networks include the broader adoption of cloud computing and machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, encompassing applications such as video surveillance, video streaming, smart meters, and health monitoring. Furthermore, emerging technologies such as beyond 5G and 6G, and high-speed passive optical networks (PONs), will further accelerate this trend [1], [2]. As spectral efficiency (SE) approaches its fundamental limit, the capacity of C-band systems will stagnate. To meet the ever-increasing demand for capacity, research efforts are being dedicated to exploring alternatives to increase the capacity of optical systems.

One of the most promising strategies to address the anticipated capacity crunch in optical communication networks is to expand the transmission bandwidth of existing systems through multi-band (MB) transmission. Standard single-mode

fiber, such as ITU-T G.652D, supports a broad low-loss transmission window spanning ~ 54 THz across the O-, E-, S-, C-, and L-bands. Fig 1 illustrates the frequency-dependent attenuation across this spectrum, highlighting the low-loss transmission window. This spectrum offers the potential for more than a tenfold increase in usable bandwidth compared to conventional systems that operate solely within the C-band, which is limited to about 4.8 THz.

However, this theoretical gain is hampered by practical limitations. For instance, transmission bands outside the C-band typically exhibit inferior optical performance due to higher attenuation, increased nonlinearities (e.g., in O \rightarrow S bands), and less mature amplification technologies. As a result, the full bandwidth expansion does not directly translate into a proportional increase in the total capacity of the system.

To mitigate these challenges, while still enhancing capacity, a more incremental approach has gained traction: extending the amplifier bandwidth within the C-band itself. Commercial systems are increasingly adopting amplifiers capable of operating over a 6 THz range (referred to as a "super band"), up from the traditional 4.8 THz. This strategy enables capacity scaling without the added complexity and cost of deploying additional amplification bands, band multiplexers, and demultiplexers required for full MB operation [3]. MB transmission can then leverage the super bands (e.g., to realize a Super-C+L-band system [4]). For more substantial capacity gains, MB transmission can be combined with spatial-division multiplexing (SDM) techniques. These include the use of multiple fibers

Fig. 1: Frequency-dependent fiber loss coefficient across ITU-T bands.

Fig. 2: Representation of the optimization variables.

(MF), multi-core or multi-mode fibers (MCF/MMF), and few-mode fibers (FMF), which exploit parallel spatial paths to further increase throughput.

This work analyzes the optical performance and capacity of single- and multi-band transmission systems, ranging from a 6 THz single super band to a 24 THz four-super-band configuration. To limit the stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) effect and system complexity, contiguous spectral occupation is capped at 18 THz (equivalent to three super bands). Systems using all four bands include a 17 THz guard band between the super O-band and the others, effectively isolating it and minimizing any SRS-induced power transfer. Configurations include Super-C, Super-C+L, Super-S+C+L, and Super-S+C+L+O systems. A 4.8 THz C-band-only system is also evaluated for benchmarking. This framework enables comparison of the spectral efficiency, complexity, capacity, and fiber requirements.

II. SIMULATION SETUP

Table I summarizes the four configurations of the MBT system analyzed in this work. All systems include a minimum 500 GHz guard band between adjacent bands. As a reference, we first consider a C-band system spanning 191.3–196.1 THz. The Super-C system extends this to 190.8–196.8 THz. The Super-C+L system covers 184.3–196.8 THz (using the super C and super L bands), while the Super-S+C+L system spans 184.3–203.3 THz (using the super S, super C and super L bands). Finally, the Super-S+C+L+O configuration adds the Super O band (220.5–226.5 THz) to the three-band system, maintaining a guard band of over 17 THz from the S-band, as recommended in [5], [6]. In this case, nonlinear interference (NLI) and the SRS-induced power transfer between the O-band and other bands are considered negligible. Although some transmission bands are formally defined with bandwidths exceeding 6 THz, we assume that the optical amplifiers used across these bands will have the same bandwidth as those in the super C-band, due to the challenges in extending amplifier bandwidth.

A local span optimization approach is employed to determine the optimal launch power. The transmission system is modeled as a single optical fiber span followed by an optical amplifier. Each spectral band is supported by a dedicated amplifier with different doping materials for individual bands,

TABLE I: Minimum and maximum frequencies of each amplification band used in this work.

Band	Super L	C	Super C	Super S	Super O
Start Freq. [THz]	184.3	191.3	190.8	197.3	220.5
Stop Freq. [THz]	190.3	196.1	196.8	203.3	226.5

TABLE II: Required OSNR (defined in 0.1 nm) and SNR for each considered bit rate.

Bit rate [Gb/s]	400	500	600	700	800
OSNR _{req} [dB]	20	21.8	23.5	25.8	27
SNR _{req} [dB]	10.2	12.0	13.7	16.0	17.2

necessitating the use of band-specific demultiplexers and multiplexers at each amplification site [7].

The transmission system operates with 40 channels per super band and 32 channels within the C-band, all spaced on a 150 GHz channel grid. Each channel carries a 120 GBd signal shaped with a roll-off factor of 0.15.

The optical fiber is modeled according to the ITU-T G.652.D specification, featuring a chromatic dispersion of 16.8 ps/nm/km at a wavelength of 1550 nm and a dispersion slope of 0.058 ps/nm²/km. The nonlinear coefficient and Raman gain characteristics are adopted from the model described in [8]. The fiber attenuation profile is presented in Fig. 1. Additional losses include 0.25 dB at both the input and output connectors, and splice losses of 0.01 dB/km.

Optical amplifiers are characterized by constant noise figures: 5 dB for the super L and super C/C bands, and 7 dB for the super S and super O bands. The total insertion loss introduced by the multiplexing and demultiplexing components is assumed to be 1.5 dB.

A. Power Optimization

We use the per-channel GSNR as the quality of transmission (QoT) estimation (considering the signal bandwidth as a reference). This QoT metric is given by:

$$\text{GSNR} = \frac{P_i}{P_i^{\text{ASE}} + P_i^{\text{NLI}}} \quad (1)$$

where P_i is the power of channel i and P_i^{ASE} and P_i^{NLI} are the power of the Gaussian noise corresponding to the amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise and the nonlinear interference due to the self- and cross-channel nonlinear crosstalk at channel i , respectively. The NLI noise contribution is calculated using the GGN model [9] and the SRS is calculated by numerically solving the Raman equations that govern this effect [10]. Both methods are available in the open-source python library GNPY [11].

The objective of launch power optimization is to maximize the overall system GSNR while minimizing GSNR fluctuations across each spectral band. Achieving a flatter QoT profile can simplify routing and spectrum assignment (RSA) algorithms and enhance channel availability, as discussed in [12].

Fig. 3: (a) Optimized launch power and (b) resulting per-channel GSNR for a 75 km span

Fig. 4: (a) Spectral efficiency and (b) capacity of the different transmission systems for different link lengths.

Figure 2 illustrates the optimization parameters for a system operating across the S, C, and L bands. These parameters correspond to settings typically configurable on commercial optical amplifiers: the average channel power per band (P_x) and the power tilt (T_x). The power of a specific channel i in band x is defined as $P_i = (f_i - f_x)T_x$, where f_i and f_x are the channel frequency and the center frequency of band it belongs to, respectively.

To simplify the optimization process, the approach focuses on adjusting these band-level parameters rather than optimizing the power of each individual channel. This avoids the complexity of managing N_{ch}^x variables per band, where N_{ch}^x is the number of channels in that band.

Furthermore, the multivariate optimization problem is decomposed into a sequence of single-variable subproblems, which are solved iteratively until convergence is achieved. This method follows a similar strategy to the one proposed in [7].

After optimization, we evaluate the capacity and spectral efficiency of the different transmission systems in a point-to-point link with a variable number of 75 km spans. For each band, the GSNR of channel i at the end of a lightpath with N spans of length L_n is given by:

$$\text{GSNR}_N(i) = \text{GSNR}_{OPT}^{L_N}(i) - 10 \log_{10}(N) - M \quad (2)$$

where $\text{GSNR}_{OPT}^{L_N}(i)$ is the optimized single-span GSNR of channel i and M is the system margin defined as $M = 1 + 0.05N_{OLAs}$. The system margin comprises a fixed 1 dB

margin and a variable contribution that depends on the number of optical amplifiers traversed (N_{OLAs}).

A lightpath is feasible for a given signal configuration and transmission band if the required SNR is less than GSNR_N . In this work, five different bit rates are considered and their required OSNR and SNR are presented in Table II. These values were taken from the OpenRoadm multi-source agreement (MSA) [13] for 400 Gb/s and 800 Gb/s formats at 118 GBd (the values for the remaining bit rates were linearly interpolated). The SNR_{req} values are calculated directly from the OSNR_{req} values using the relation given in [14], that is, $\text{SNR}_{req} = \text{OSNR}_{req} - 10 \log_{10}(R_S/B_{ref})$, with B_{ref} equal to 12.5 GHz.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 3a and 3b present: optimized launch power and GSNR profiles for a single 75 km span across various systems: C, Super-C, Super-C+L, Super-S+C+L, and Super-S+C+L+O. Among these, single-band systems exhibit the highest average GSNR (27.0 dB and 26.9 dB for the C and Super-C systems, respectively). This advantage stems from the absence of additional MUX/DEMUX losses, lower fiber attenuation, reduced nonlinear effects, and lower amplifier noise figures compared to MB systems.

The figures also reveal that incorporating the Super S-band into a Super-C+L system enhances GSNR in the super C and super L bands. This improvement is due to inter-band power transfer, where super S-band channels act as co-propagating

Fig. 5: Number of required parallel fibers to achieve a $120\times$ capacity increase of the C-band-only system for different point-to-point link lengths.

Raman pumps, enhancing power transfer via the SRS effect. However, the super S and super O bands show significantly lower average GSNR, with the super O band performing the worst.

These GSNR variations across bands result in diverse capacity-reach profiles for each system. To illustrate this, consider a link composed of 75 km spans and a transceiver operating in the modes listed in Table II. Each bit rate corresponds to a specific modulation format, selected based on the available GSNR and predefined thresholds listed in Table II.

Figures 4a and 4b show the spectral efficiency vs. reach and capacity vs. reach profiles, respectively, with reach measured in 75 km spans. Single-band systems consistently achieve the highest SE due to their superior average GSNR on a single span ($GSNR_{OPT}^{Ln}$). The maximum SE of 5.33 bit/s/Hz (meaning that all channels transmit 800 Gb/s) is maintained at a maximum of 6 spans for the C and Super-C systems, 5 spans for the Super-C+L, 3 for the Super-S+C+L and 1 span for the Super-S+C+L+O system.

Despite the superior average GSNR of single-band systems, multi-band systems generally offer higher total capacity across most distances, thanks to their greater channel count. The capacity gain from adding an amplification band is most pronounced at shorter distances, where the optical performance degradation is less severe. For example, adding the super L band to a Super-C system doubles the capacity (from 32 to 64 Tb/s) for links up to 375 km. However, this gain diminishes with distance and disappears beyond 1800 km.

Adding the super S band to a Super-C+L system yields a smaller benefit: a 50% capacity increase for links up to 225 km, tapering off to no gain beyond 1800 km. Compared to a system with Super-C only, the Super-S+C+L configuration triples the link capacity to 225 km.

The super O band supports transmission only over distances up to 450 km. When added to a Super-S+C+L system, it increases capacity by 33% for a single 75 km span. However, this benefit gradually decreases with distance, becoming negligible at 450 km. Beyond this point, the capacities of the Super-S+C+L and Super-S+C+L+O systems are the same (because of

TABLE III: Required parallel fibers to achieve a 120 times capacity increase of the C-band-only system for selected reaches.

System	Reach [km]			
	75	300	675	1425
C	120	120	120	120
Super-C	96	96	96	96
Super-C+L	48	48	52	54
Super-S+C+L	32	34	38	54
Super-S+C+L+O	24	28	38	54

the guard band between the super O and the other bands). As a result, the SE of the Super-S+C+L+O system drops sharply from 450 to 525 km, since the super O-band channels, which initially carried 400 Gb/s, cease to transmit any data.

Lastly, Fig. 5 illustrates the number of parallel fibers required by various transmission systems to achieve a capacity 120 times greater than that of a single-fiber C-band only system, across different link lengths. Table III complements this figure by providing specific values for 75 km, 300 km, 675 km, and 1425 km.

As expected, the C-band-only system consistently requires 120 parallel fibers at all distances. The Super-C system typically requires 96 parallel fibers across most distances, due to its similar average GSNR and 20% higher channel count compared to the C-band only system. Minor deviations at 525, 750, 1050, and 1500 km arise from slight GSNR differences and the limited set of transceiver operating modes. For instance, while the C-band-only system may transmit at 800 Gb/s at a certain distance and frequency slot, the Super-C system might drop to 700 Gb/s due to a marginal GSNR reduction (0.1 dB), lacking an intermediate mode closer to 800 Gb/s.

The trends for the other systems mirror their respective capacity curves. The inclusion of the super O band allows us to reduce the number of required fibers only for links up to 450 km –for instance, for a 300 km link, only 23.3% of the 120 fibers are required. Beyond 450 km, the Super-S+C+L and Super-S+C+L+O systems require the same number of fibers. For a target 675 km link, the former provides the same capacity as 120 parallel C-band systems with only 31.7% of the fibers.

Since only the super L band in these MB systems maintains GSNR levels comparable to single-band systems, while the super C, super S, and super O bands have lower GSNR, the number of required fibers increases rapidly beyond 1575 km (for the Super-C+L system) and 1750 km (for the Super-S+C+L and Super-S+C+L+O systems), eventually converging to 96, matching the Super-C system. Still, for a target 1425 km link, a Super-C+L-band system can offer the same capacity as the reference (120 fiber) C-band system at the expense of only 45% of the number of fibers.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Multi-band transmission offers a cost-effective route to significantly increase the capacity of existing optical systems, leveraging the wide low-loss window (54 THz) of ITU-T G.652D fiber. However, adding more amplification bands tends

to reduce spectral efficiency, particularly over long distances. As a result, full exploitation of the entire 54 THz window remains impractical for data transmission. This work analyzed the optical performance and capacity of four MBT system configurations: Super-C, Super-C+L, Super-S+C+L and Super-S+C+L+O, and compared them to the benchmark C-band-only system.

Results indicate that a practical balance between spectral efficiency and bandwidth expansion appears to be the use of two or three super bands, each occupying 6 THz (such as Super-C+L or Super-S+C+L). For localized capacity upgrades in smaller network segments, the super O band can be selectively deployed.

This capacity enhancement translates into a reduced need for parallel fibers to increase the capacity of a single-fiber single-band system with 4.8 THz. For a 75 km link, the number of required fibers drops by 20%, 60%, 73%, and 80% for the Super-C, Super-C+L, Super-S+C+L, and Super-S+C+L+O systems, respectively. At 1425 km, the reductions are more modest for the multi-band systems: 20% for Super-C and 45% for the other multi-band systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work received funding from the SNS Joint Undertaken Grant Agreement 101096120 (SEASON) and was supported by FCT/MECI through national funds and when applicable co-funded EU funds under UID/50008: Instituto de Telecomunicações.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cisco, "Cisco annual internet report (2018–2023) white paper," tech report, Cisco, 2020.
- [2] M. Z. Chowdhury, M. Shahjalal, S. Ahmed, and Y. M. Jang, "6G wireless communication systems: Applications, requirements, technologies, challenges, and research directions," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 1, pp. 957–975, 2020.
- [3] Rob Shore, "Optical networking in 2024 - lighting the way forward." [Online]. Available: <https://www.thefastmode.com/expert-opinion/34436-optical-networking-in-2024-lighting-the-way-forward>.
- [4] J. Pedro and A. Souza, "Impact of channel provisioning strategies in the transient resiliency of SuperC+L-band networks," in *2024 14th International Workshop on Resilient Networks Design and Modeling (RNDM)*, pp. 1–7, 2024.
- [5] N. Sambo, B. Correia, A. Napoli, J. Pedro, L. Kiani, P. Castoldi, and V. Curri, "Network upgrade exploiting multi band: S- or E-band?," *J. Opt. Commun. Netw.*, vol. 14, pp. 749–756, Sep 2022.
- [6] A. Souza, N. Costa, and J. Pedro, "Performance and transient-resiliency of S- and E-band upgrades of a C+L-band system," in *Optical Fiber Communication Conference (OFC) 2025*, p. M4G.6, Optica Publishing Group, 2025.
- [7] A. Souza, N. Costa, J. Pedro, and J. Pires, "Benefits of counterpropagating Raman amplification for multiband optical networks," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 562–571, 2022.
- [8] A. Souza, B. Correia, A. Napoli, V. Curri, N. Costa, J. Pedro, and J. Pires, "Cost analysis of ultrawideband transmission in optical networks," *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 81–93, 2024.
- [9] M. Cantono, D. Pileri, A. Ferrari, C. Catanese, J. Thouras, J.-L. Auge, and V. Curri, "On the interplay of nonlinear interference generation with stimulated Raman scattering for QoT estimation," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 36, p. 3131–3141, Aug. 2018.
- [10] D. Christodoulides and R. Jander, "Evolution of stimulated Raman crosstalk in wavelength division multiplexed systems," *IEEE Photonics Technology Letters*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 1722–1724, 1996.
- [11] OOPT-PSE team within the Telecom Infra Project, "Github repository of GNPpy." [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Telecominfraproject/oopt-gnpy>.
- [12] M. Menif, L. Rusch, and M. Karasek, "Application of preemphasis to achieve flat output OSNR in time-varying channels in cascaded EDFAs without equalization," *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 19, no. 10, pp. 1440–1452, 2001.
- [13] Open ROADM MSA, "Open ROADM MSA Specification ver 7.0." [Online]. Available: https://github.com/OpenROADM/OpenROADM_MSA_Public.
- [14] R.-J. Essiambre and R. W. Tkach, "Capacity trends and limits of optical communication networks," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 100, no. 5, pp. 1035–1055, 2012.